

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(СНИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ISSN 2181-1482

DOI JOURNAL 10.26739/2181-1482

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 2

INNOVATIONS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 2

ТАШКЕНТ-2025

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ INNOVATIONS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

№2 (2025) DOI <http://dx.doi.org/10.26739/2181-1482-2025-2>

Главный редактор | Chief Editor:

МАГРУПОВ АБДУЛЛА МАХМУДОВИЧ
кандидат технических наук, доцент
Исполнительный директор Филиала РГУ
нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И. М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

Ответственный редактор | Executive Editor

ДЖУМАБАЕВ ДАВЛАТБАЙ ХАЛИЛЛАЕВИЧ
заместитель директора по научным работам и
инновациям, доктор физико-математических наук,
доцент Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И. М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

РЕДАКЦИОННЫЙ СОВЕТ | EDITORIAL BOARD

АХМЕДОВ МИРЗААНВАР МОХИДЖОНОВИЧ
PhD, заместитель директора по учебной работе Филиала РГУ
нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И. М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

АКРАМОВ БАХШИЛЛО ШАФИЕВИЧ
кандидат технических наук, профессор
отделения «Разработка нефтяных, газовых и газоконденсатных
месторождений» Филиала РГУ нефти
и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

БУЗРУКОВ РУСТАМ ИСЛАМОВИЧ
кандидат сельскохозяйственных наук, доцент кафедры «Физика,
электротехника и теплотехника» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

БЕРОВА ИННА ГРИГОРЬЕВНА
доцент кафедры «Бурение нефтяных и газовых скважин» РГУ нефти и
газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина (г. Москва), кандидат технических наук

КАДИРБЕКОВА ДУРДОНА ХИКМАТУЛЛАЕВНА
PhD, доцент, заведующая кафедрой «Иностранные языки»
Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

МУХАМЕДОВ ШУХРАТ БАХРОНОВИЧ
доктор исторических наук, доцент кафедры
«Социально-гуманитарных дисциплин» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

МАВЛЯНКАРИЕВ БАХТИЁР АБДУГАФУРОВИЧ
доктор технических наук, профессор
отделения «Проектирование, сооружение и эксплуатация систем
трубопроводного транспорта» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте.

НАДИРОВ КАЗИМ САДЫКОВИЧ
доктор технических наук, профессор кафедры нефтегазового дела Южно-
Казахстанского университета имени Мухтара Ауэзова (Казахстан)

ОТТО ОЛЬГА ЭДГАРОВНА
Кандидат экономических наук, доцент, заведующая кафедрой
«Экономика нефти и газа» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

РАХИМОВ АНВАРХОДЖА АКБАРХОДЖАЕВИЧ
доктор технических наук, доцент отделения «Бурение
нефтяных и газовых скважин» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

РАВИЛОВ ШАВКАТ МУГАВЕЕВИЧ
доцент, заведующий кафедры «Математика и информатика» Филиала
РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

СИДИКОВ АБДУЖАЛИЛ СИДИКОВИЧ
доктор химических наук, профессор, заведующий кафедрой «Общая
химия и химия нефти и газа» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

САПАЕВ УСМАН КАЛАНДАРОВИЧ
доктор физико-математических наук, доцент, заведующий кафедрой
«Физика, электротехника и теплотехника» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ЮЛДАШЕВА ЛОЛИТА ЛУКМАНОВНА
преподаватель кафедры «Иностранные языки»
Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ) имени
И. М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

МАДРАХИМОВА ГУЛАСАЛ РУЗИМБАЕВНА
Первый заместитель директора по вопросам молодёжи и
духовно-просветительской работе, PhD Филиала РГУ нефти
и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

АЗИМОВ ДИЛМУРОД
доктор технических наук (DSc), профессор
Гавайского университета в Маноа (США)

ГЛЕБОВА ЕЛЕНА ВИТАЛЬЕВНА
доктор технических наук, профессор,
заведующая кафедрой «Промышленная безопасность
и охрана окружающей среды» РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И. М. Губкина (г. Москва)

ДЖАМАЛОВ СИРОЖИДДИН ЗУХРИДДИНОВИЧ
доктор физико-математических наук, главный научный сотрудник
лаборатории «Научная лаборатория дифференциальных уравнений и их
приложений» Института математики имени В.И. Романовского
Академии наук Республики Узбекистан

ЗАКИРОВ АЛИМДЖАН АБДУРАХИМОВИЧ
доктор технических наук, профессор кафедры «Экономика нефти и
газа» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

НУРМАТОВ УСАН ДАУРОВИЧ
кандидат технических наук, доцент отделения «Бурение
нефтяных и газовых скважин» Филиала РГУ
нефти и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХАИРОВА ДИНАРА РИМОВНА
кандидат экономических наук, профессор
кафедры «Экономика нефти и газа» Филиала РГУ нефти
и газа (НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ХУСАНОВ СУЛТАНБОЙ ТУХТАЕВИЧ
доктор геолого-минералогических наук, профессор
отделения «Технологии геологической и геофизической
разведки» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа (НИУ)
имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

УСМАНОВА АЗИЗА АБДУЛЛАЖАНОВНА
кандидат психологических наук, доцент, награждена нагрудным
знаком «Отличник высшего образования», заведующая кафедрой
«Социально-гуманитарных дисциплин» Филиала РГУ нефти и газа
(НИУ) имени И.М. Губкина в г. Ташкенте

ЭФЕНДИЕВ ГАЛИБ МАМЕДОВИЧ
руководитель отдела «Теоретические и прикладные проблемы
современного бурения» института нефти и газа Министерства науки и
образования Азербайджанской республики. д.т.н., профессор, член-
корреспондент Национальной академии наук Азербайджана
(Азербайджан)

DESIGN-PAГEMAKER | ДИЗАЙН - ВЕРСТКА: ХУРШИД МИРЗАХМЕДОВ

КОНТАКТ РЕДАКЦИЙ ЖУРНАЛОВ. WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ
ООО Tadqiqot город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000

EDITORIAL STAFF OF THE JOURNALS OF WWW.TADQIQOT.UZ
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

МУНДАРИЖА | СОДЕРЖАНИЕ | CONTENT

1. Акрамов Б.Ш., Адизов Б.З., Нуриддинов Ж.Ф, Евстафеев Е.А ОБВОДНЕННОСТЬ ГАЗОВЫХ СКВАЖИН ОСНОВНЫЕ ВЫЗОВЫ И ПОДХОДЫ К ИХ РЕШЕНИЮ.....	4
2. Ахмедов М.М., Саиджонов Ш.С. АНАЛИЗ ФАКТОРОВ ПРИВЛЕЧЕНИЯ ИНОСТРАННЫХ СТУДЕНТОВ В УЗБЕКИСТАН.....	9
3. Журава Г.С. СРАВНИТЕЛЬНЫЙ АНАЛИЗ ФОРМ РЕЧЕВОГО ЭТИКЕТА В АНГЛИЙСКОМ И УЗБЕКСКОМ ЯЗЫКАХ С РИТОРИЧЕСКОЙ ТОЧКИ ЗРЕНИЯ.....	18
4. Иргашева О.И., Пулатова А.В. TIME-LAPSE ГЕОФИЗИКА КАК ИНСТРУМЕНТ ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИ БЕЗОПАСНОГО МОНИТОРИНГА МИГРАЦИИ ФЛЮИДОВ В НЕДРАХ.....	24
5. Кадирбекова Д.Х., Мухамедов Ш.Б., Хакбердиев Э.Н. СОВЕРШЕНСТВОВАНИЕ ПОДГОТОВКИ СПЕЦИАЛИСТОВ В ОБЛАСТИ ЭКОНОМИКИ И МЕНЕДЖМЕНТА В УСЛОВИЯХ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ ОБРАЗОВАТЕЛЬНЫХ ПРИОРИТЕТОВ.....	31
6. Кадирбекова Д.Х., Садуллаева М.А. ЛИНГВОСТИЛИСТИЧЕСКИЕ И ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПЕРЕВОДА ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНОЙ ЛЕКСИКИ НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ (НА МАТЕРИАЛЕ АНГЛИЙСКОГО И РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКОВ)	36
7. Матякубова П.М., Сайдорипов Л.Ф. РОЛЬ МЕТРОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ИНСТИТУТОВ В ИНФРАСТРУКТУРЕ КАЧЕСТВ.....	42
8. Матякубова П. М., Шамуратов Д.У. УСТРОЙСТВО ДЛЯ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ВЯЗКОСТИ ТЕЧУЩИХ ЖИДКОСТЕЙ В ТРУБАХ МАЛОГО ДИАМЕТРА.....	49
9. Нурматов У.Д., Ильюшин И.П. РАСПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ СКОРОСТИ В СЕЧЕНИИ ТРУБЫ ПРИ ЛАМИНАРНОМ ДВИЖЕНИИ ЖИДКОСТИ.....	57
10. Нурматов У.Д., Цой А.О. ГИДРОСТАТИЧЕСКОЕ ДАВЛЕНИЕ И ЕГО СВОЙСТВА В БУРЕНИИ.....	61
11. Такташева Д.Р., Кодиржонова Р.А. РОЛЬ ПЕРЕВОДА ТЕХНИЧЕСКОЙ ДОКУМЕНТАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ..	65
12. Хусанов С.Т., Каланходжаева Ш.Т. КОМПЛЕКСНЫЕ ЛИТОЛОГО-ФАЦИАЛЬНЫЕ И ФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ПРЕДПОСЫЛКИ НЕФТЕГАЗОНОСНОСТИ ВЕРХНЕГО ПАЛЕОЗОЯ ЮЖНОЙ ФЕРГАНЫ.....	69
13. Хусанов С.Т., Алимов М.М., Арапова М.А., Жураев А.А. УСЛОВИЯ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ И СТРОЕНИЕ ВЕРХНЕЮРСКОЙ КАРБОНАТНОЙ ФОРМАЦИИ БУХАРО-ХИВИНСКОЙ НЕФТЕГАЗОНОСНОЙ ОБЛАСТИ.....	72
14. Хасанова М.Б., Алтухов Я.Ю. ПЕРЕХОД К «ЗЕЛЕННОЙ» ЭКОНОМИКЕ: ПРИОРИТЕТНЫЕ НАПРАВЛЕНИЯ УЧАСТИЯ ОБЩЕСТВЕННОСТИ.....	77

УДК: 532.135:681.2

Matyakubova P.,

Tashkent State Technical University named after
I. Karimov, University. Professor
Head of Department of Metrology, Technical Regulation
Standardization and Certification
e-mail: tgtu_mss@rambler.ru

Shamuratov D.U.

Urgench Ranch University of Technology
Department of Mechanical engineering
and information technologies. Teacher
e-mail: jamshid.shamuratov.phd2022@gmail.com

**DEVICE FOR DETERMINING THE VISCOSITY OF FLOWING LIQUIDS IN SMALL
DIAMETER PIPES**<http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16573411>**ABSTRACT**

With the spread of lubricants, the use of viscosity has become more and more important in various fields. In this article, the viscosity value of fluids in production processes is used to determine the relationship between the change in fluid temperature. As a result of research, the author found that the temperature of lubricating oils and other complex liquids moving in pipes changes depending on their viscosity. According to the results of this research, the enterprise may be able to determine and continuously monitor the viscosity of products during the production process or during their movement in pipelines.

Keywords: kinematic viscosity, temperature, viscometry, thermoresistor, small pipe.

Матякубова П.М.

Ташкентский государственный технический университет
имени И. Каримова
Профессор
Заведующая кафедрой метрологии
технического регулирования в институте стандартизации и сертификации
e-mail: tgtu_mss@rambler.ru

Шамуратов Д.У.

Ургенчский филиал Технологического университета
Кафедра машиностроения и информационных технологий
Преподаватель
e-mail: jamshid.shamuratov.phd2022@gmail.com

УСТРОЙСТВО ДЛЯ ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЯ ВЯЗКОСТИ ТЕЧУЩИХ ЖИДКОСТЕЙ В ТРУБАХ МАЛОГО ДИАМЕТРА

АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье рассматривается использование величины вязкости жидкостей в производственных процессах для определения взаимосвязи между изменением температуры жидкости. В результате проведённых исследований авторы установили, что температура смазочных масел и других сложных жидкостей, движущихся по трубам, изменяется в зависимости от их вязкости. Согласно результатам этого исследования предприятие может определить и непрерывно контролировать вязкость продукции как в процессе производства, так и при транспортировке по трубопроводам.

Ключевые слова: кинематическая вязкость, температура, вискозиметрия, терморезистор, малая труба.

Matyakubova P.M.

I. Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti. Professor
Metrologiya, texnik tartibga solish,
standartlashtirish va sertifikatlashtirish kafedrasini mudiri
e-mail: tgtu_mss@rambler.ru

Shamuratov D.Y.

Urganch Texnologiya Universiteti filiali
Mashinasozlik va axborot texnologiyalari kafedrasini. O'qituvchi
e-mail: jamshid.shamuratov.phd2022@gmail.com

KICHIK DIAMETRLI QUVURLARDA OQUVCHI SUYUQLIKLARNING VAZKOZLIGINI ANIQLASH QURILMASI

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu maqolada ishlab chiqarish jarayonlarida suyuqliklarning viskozlik qiymatidan foydalanib, ularning haroratidagi o'zgarish o'rtasidagi bog'liqlik aniqlangan. Tadqiqotlar natijasida mualliflar quvurlar orqali harakatlanayotgan moylovchi va boshqa murakkab suyuqliklarning harorati ularning viskozligiga bog'liq tarzda o'zgarishini aniqladi. Ushbu tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, korxonada ishlab chiqarish jarayonida yoki mahsulot quvurlar bo'ylab harakat qilayotganda viskozlikni aniqlash va doimiy monitoring qilish imkoniyatiga ega bo'ladi.

Kalit so'zlar: kinematik viskozlik, harorat, viskozimetr, termorezistor, kichik quvur.

Introduction

When liquid or gas moves in pipes and channels, two different modes of motion are observed: laminar and turbulent. The laminar mode of motion (from the Latin lamina - layered) is characterized by the fact that the liquid flow moves in separate streams or layers, and the trajectories of individual particles of liquid do not intersect each other, and the streamlines coincide with the trajectories of the particles. Laminar motion is completely ordered and, at constant pressure, strictly established. The turbulent mode of motion (from the Latin turbulentus - vortex) is accompanied by intensive mixing of liquid volumes, which, in addition to longitudinal movement along the channel, acquire transverse and rotational motion, which causes pulsations in time of speed and pressure at each point of the flow.

The Reynolds number at which the transition from laminar to turbulent flow occurs is called critical.

The critical Reynolds number for a circular pipe is \longrightarrow $Re_{кр} = 2320$.

The fluid flow is laminar \longrightarrow if $Re < Re_{кр}$.

The fluid flow is turbulent \longrightarrow if $Re > Re_{кр}$.

It should be borne in mind that at $Re = 2000 \div 3000$, both turbulent and laminar modes can occur.

Methods for determining the Reynolds number Re :

- a) Analytical definition. The Reynolds number is defined as a dimensionless quantity expressing the ratio of inertial forces to viscous forces in a flow of liquid or gas.
- b) Graphical method (diagrams and nomograms). For problems with typical flows, for example, in pipes or channels, diagrams are used, such as:
- c) Moody diagram: relates the Reynolds number, friction coefficient and roughness.
- d) Nomograms for flows: allow Re to be determined based on experimental data and the geometry of the system.
- e) Experimental method. In laboratory conditions, the Reynolds number is determined based on direct measurements of the velocity, viscosity and density of the liquid.

The following items are used:

- a) Flow velocity meters (anemometers, ultrasonic sensors).
- b) Viscosity analyzers: allow you to determine the viscosity of the liquid.
- c) Geometric parameters: are determined directly (e.g., pipe diameter).
- d) The proposed viscometer belongs to the field of measuring the viscosity of liquids (viscometry) and can be used to determine the kinematic viscosity of chemical solutions, alcohols, oil and oil products moving in small diameter pipes in various fields of technology and production.

The proposed viscometer is related to measuring technology. The proposed viscometer refers to methods of continuous measurement of the viscosity of an incompressible fluid flowing through pipe networks (Newtonian, non-Newtonian or multicomponent mixture).

Determination of the viscosity of liquids by capillary, rotational and vibration viscometers is one of the most common. Capillary viscometers are not used in industries that require high accuracy due to their low measurement accuracy. Rotational viscometers, on the other hand, are among the most widely used viscometers, which are distinguished by the fact that they can be used for all liquids and have a wide measurement range. Oscillation viscometers, in turn, are distinguished from other types of viscometers by having many advantages.

As a proposed viscometer, the proposed viscometer is designed to determine or monitor the kinematic viscosity of fluids moving in small diameter pipelines in industrial plants and oil and gas processing plants. As a proposed viscometer, the proposed viscometer can be used to determine the kinematic viscosity of low-viscosity liquids.

One of the important controlled parameters of oil during production and pipeline transportation is viscosity [the following patents are SU 427260, 08/10/1968, G01L 27/00; SU 1500909, 29.12.1986, G01N 11/08; SU 1205001, 09/12/1958, B01D 24/48, B01D 02/21; SU 1413481, 02/02/1987, G01N 11/08; RU 2390733; 09/07/2006, G01F 1/84, G01F 1/74, G01F 25/00, G01F 1/34; RU 2414686, 19.07.2007, G01F 1/32, G01F 15/00; RU 2521721, 31.01.2013, G01F 1/00; RU 2451911, 22/12/2008, G01F 15/18 on determining the viscosities of liquids in pipelines].

Materials and methods

Currently, the viscosity of oil in oil production wells is regularly monitored by taking periodic samples to measure the viscosity of the samples under laboratory conditions.

The certificate for the proposed viscometer RU 2743511 C1 G01F 1/66 (2006.01) provides the calculation of the kinematic viscosity of the extracted oil in the pipeline based on the speed of oil movement in the pipeline and the internal diameter of the pipeline. But it should also be said that the speed of the liquid in the pipe is not always constant.

That is why, to determine the viscosity of liquids using a new design solution and a mathematical expression that is independent of the speed of the liquid and the internal diameter of the main pipe and depends on the specific heat capacity, which is one of the main physical and chemical properties of liquids. the structure was developed.

As a proposed viscometer, the proposed viscometer (Fig. 1) is composed of the following parts: liquid moving pipe 1, liquid moving in the pipe 2, inner wall inside the pipe 3, small pipe connected to the main pipe 4, liquid heating device 5, liquid heating thermoresistor 6, thermoresistor 7, for determining the temperature of the heated liquid, unit for determining the viscosity of the liquid 8, holes opened on both sides 9, for connecting the liquid moving pipe 1.

Figure 1. Structure of a viscometer for determining the viscosity of liquids moving in small diameter pipes.

As a proposed viscometer, the proposed viscometer works as follows: when the liquid 2 starts to move from the pipe, the liquid 2 starts moving through the liquid moving pipe 1 of the viscometer, and by hitting the inner wall of the pipe 3, it ensures the movement of the liquid 2 to the small pipe 4 connected to the main pipe. The viscosity of liquid 2, which starts to move in the small pipe 4, is determined by the viscosity determination unit 8. In the viscosity determination unit 8, the liquid 2 moving through the liquid heating device 5 is heated by a thermoresistor 6 with a specific temperature T_1 . The temperature T_2 of the liquid heated to a certain temperature is determined through the thermoresistor 7. The difference between the temperatures of thermoresistors 6 and 7 determines the viscosity of the liquid through ΔT (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Schematic structure of the dimensions of the viscometer for determining the viscosity of liquids moving in small diameter pipes.

Any liquid or body has a specific heat capacity, which is a quantity describing the increase in temperature of a certain amount of heat energy to a liquid or body. The proposed viscometer also determines the kinematic viscosity of the liquid based on the determination of the change in temperature depending on the specific heat capacity of the liquid.

$$v = \frac{\eta}{\rho} \tag{1}$$

Where, v - kinematic viscosity of liquid, cCt ; η - dinamic viscosity of liquid, $mPa \cdot s$; ρ - density of liquid, kg/m^3 .

$$\Delta T = T_2 - T_1 = \frac{P_{qiz}}{c \cdot m'} \tag{2}$$

in which: P_{qiz} - the unit amount of energy used for heating by the heating installation 5, W ; c is the specific heat capacity coefficient of liquid 2, $J/kg \cdot K$; m' - unit amount of liquid mass heated by thermoresistor 6, kg ($m' = m/t$ is unit amount of time, s).

The value of the specific heat capacity coefficient c of the liquid is given in the reference books or in the physico-chemical properties of liquids.

It is desirable to use the value of the relative heat capacity coefficient c when the liquid 2 moves inside the pipe 1 at a constant speed v or moves in a laminar flow. To ensure a constant speed, an inner ring 2 is made in the pipe 1, which prevents the movement of the liquid and ensures its constant movement into the small pipe 4.

Laminar fluid flow can be determined by the value of Reynolds number (Re). For the liquid to move through laminar flow, it should not be less than the following value

$$Re = 1 \cdot 10 \div 1 \cdot 10^3 \tag{3}$$

Reynolds number (Re) is defined as follows:

$$Re = \frac{vd}{\nu} = \frac{\rho \cdot v \cdot d}{\eta} \tag{4}$$

where: ν – kinematic viscosity of liquid, $c\text{Ct}$; d -diameter of the liquid moving pipe, mm; v - speed of movement of liquid in the pipe, m/s.

$$P_{qiz} = \frac{W}{t} \tag{4}$$

where, P_{qiz} –the unit amount of energy used for heating by the heating device 5, W; W is the consumed energy of heating device 5, J; t is unit amount of time, s t –(the time spent on heating by the heating device or the time spent on passing through the gap between two speed resistors 6 and 7 during the movement of the liquid).

Substituting expression (4) into expression (1), we determine the following equality (5):

$$\Delta T = \frac{P_{qiz}}{c \cdot m'} = P_{qiz} \cdot \frac{1}{c \cdot \frac{m}{t}} = \frac{W}{t} \cdot \frac{1}{c \cdot \frac{m}{t}} = \frac{W}{c \cdot m} \Rightarrow \Delta T = \frac{W}{c \cdot m} \tag{5}$$

In place of the mass (m) in the second part of the equation (5), we put the following expression (Fig. 2):

$$m = \rho \cdot V \tag{6}$$

Where, ρ - density of liquid, kg/m^3 ; V - the volume of liquid between 6 thermoresistors and 7 thermoresistors ($V = S \cdot L = \frac{\pi \cdot d^2}{4} \cdot L$) m^3 (Fig.3).

Figure 3. Schematic structure of the dimensions of the viscometer for determining the volume of liquids moving in small diameter pipes.

$S = \pi d^2 / 4$ expression refers to the cross-sectional area of the pipe being heated by the heating device. According to the working principle of the viscometer, the thermo-resistor 6 heats the liquid to a certain temperature. For this heating, a cylindrical thermo-resistor 6 is used along the entire diameter of the pipe (Fig. 4). Since we consider the sum of working surfaces of 6 thermoresistors to be equal to the cross-sectional surface of this pipe, the working surface of the liquid during heating $S = \pi d^2 / 4$ is calculated by this expression.

As a result, we form the following equation:

$$\Delta T = \frac{W}{c \cdot \rho \cdot S \cdot L} = \frac{W}{c \cdot \frac{\pi \cdot d^2}{4} \cdot L} = \frac{4W}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot \rho \cdot c \cdot L} \tag{7}$$

The distance L is covered by the liquid with the speed v in the time t . Find this time t , we use the time taken to change the temperature T_1 to T_2 at the start of thermoresistors 6 and 7.

$$L = v \cdot t \tag{8}$$

Substituting (8) into (7) we get the following expression

$$\Delta T = \frac{4W}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \rho \cdot v \cdot t} \tag{9}$$

Figure 4. Schematic of the location of the heating element according to the diameter of the pipe.

We determine v from (9).

$$v = \frac{4W}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \rho \cdot \Delta T \cdot t} \tag{10}$$

Substituting the expression (10) into (4), we determine the expression for determining the kinematic viscosity of the liquid:

$$Re = \frac{vd}{\nu} = \frac{4W \cdot d}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \rho \cdot \Delta T \cdot t \cdot \nu} \Rightarrow \nu = \frac{4W \cdot d}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \rho \cdot \Delta T \cdot t \cdot Re} \tag{11}$$

Substituting the expression (11) into (1), we determine the expression for determining the dynamic viscosity of the liquid:

$$\eta = \nu \cdot \rho = \frac{4W \cdot d}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \rho \cdot \Delta T \cdot t \cdot Re} \cdot \rho = \frac{4W \cdot d}{\pi \cdot d^2 \cdot c \cdot \Delta T \cdot t \cdot Re} \tag{12}$$

The value of dynamic viscosities of low-viscosity liquids is determined using the proposed viscometer by expression (12). Where π - constant value, equal to $\pi=3.14$; d - diameter of the liquid moving pipe, mm; c - the specific heat capacity coefficient of liquid 2, J/kg·K; l - the distance between thermoresistors 6 and 7, mm;

ΔT - difference between the temperatures thermoresistors 6 and 7, K; W - the consumed energy of heating device 5, J; Re -Reynolds number. The Reynolds number is determined by reference or experiment for fluids.

Results and discussion

The theoretical results of determining the kinematic viscosity of oil (Fig. 5) products (gasoline) were calculated using the expression (9). It can be noted that the accuracy of the results obtained by calculations is high and the error (3-5%) is low.

Figure 5. The amount of kinematic viscosity of petroleum products (gasoline).

Based on the above figure, it can be said that the error value between the actual kinematic viscosity of gasoline and the theoretically calculated kinematic viscosity values using the viscometer proposed in the research is low and the proposed viscometer can be used in industry. It can be added that the value of the error in the measurement shows that the pipe can heat up along with the liquid, and that all the energy used for heating is taken into account that the pipe is heated, not the liquid, and it is necessary to take into account the correction value of the viscometer through experiments.

Conclusions

As a conclusion, it can be noted that the detection and control of their viscosities in small-diameter pipelines in industrial enterprises or long distances to production zones allows to avoid risks in the transportation of liquids. Also, the correct selection of the pump and additional structures used to move and drive liquids in pipelines, together with hu, causes efficient performance of work such as energy saving. Therefore, in the above study, work aimed at calculating the viscosity of liquids moving in a pipe according to its temperature change was carried out. This, in turn, leads to new levels of production in the industry and the production of quality products.

Reference list:

1. Certificate for utility model RU 98816 U1 G01N 11/16 (2006.01).
1. Certificate for utility model RU 112769 U1 G01N 33/26 (2006.01).
2. Certificate for the proposed viscometer RU 2743511 C1 G01F 1/66 (2006.01).
3. Shamuratov, J., Mustafayev, O., Kadyrov, I. (2024). New Viscometers for Measuring the Viscosity of Liquids. *Journal of Engineering*, Article ID 6877306, 8 pages. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2024/6877306>
4. Mills, K.C., Chapman, L.A., Fox, A.B., Sridhar, D. (2001). Round robin project on estimation of slag viscosities. *Scandinavian Journal of Metallurgy*, 30, 396–403.
5. Battezzati, L., Greer, A.L. (1989). The viscosity of liquid metals and alloys. *Acta Metallurgica*, 37(7), 1791–1802.
6. Shamuratov, J., Ruziev, I., Ismailov, M., et al. (2024). New Vibration Viscometer for Measuring the Viscosity of Liquids. *Journal of Engineering Physics and Thermophysics*, 97, 947–955. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10891-024-02964-5>
7. Sasahara, S., Inaba, S., Tomita, M. (1992). New oscillating plate viscometer for instantaneous measurement of viscosity of molten slag. In: Proc. 4th Int. Conf. Molten Slags and Fluxes, 8–11 June, Sendai, Japan.
8. Liu, Z., Liu, Y., Tian, L. (2005). Experimental study on the relationship between the viscosity and concentration of glycerin. *Journal of Yan'an University (Natural Science Edition)*, 04, 58–59.
9. Matyakubova, P.M., Ismatullaev, P.R., Shamuratov, Z.U. (2024). Oscillatory Viscometer for Measuring the Viscosity of Liquids. *Journal of Engineering Physics and Thermophysics*, 97, 134–141. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10891-024-02876-4>
10. Seeton, C.J. (2006). Viscosity-temperature correlation for liquids. *Tribology Letters*, 22, 67–78.
11. Wunderlecht, R. (2004). Presented at the 2nd International Symposium on Physical Sciences in Space, Microgravity Sci. Technol. J. (Submitted), Toronto, Canada.
12. Shamuratov, J. (2023). New Vibration Viscometer for Measuring the High-Viscosity Liquids. In: Science of Youth – Science of the Future: Collection of Articles of the III Int. Scientific and Practical Conference, Petrozavodsk: ICNP "New Science", Europe, UK.
13. Braunschweig. (2004). Viscosity Standard Specimens 100B. PTB, Bundesalle, Vol. 52.
14. Seeton, C.J. (2006). Viscosity-temperature correlation for liquids. In: International Joint Tribology Conference, pp. 131–142.
15. Shamuratov, J.U. (2023). Method of viscosity measurement using a new oscillating-plate type viscometer for high-temperature. *Material Instruments*, 10.

16. Caetano, F.J.P., Fareleira, J.M.N.A., Oliveira, C.M.B.P., Wakeham, W.A. (2004). Viscosity of di-isodecylphthalate: A potential standard of moderate viscosity. *International Journal of Thermophysics*, 25(5), 1311–1322.
17. Knezevic, D., Savic, V. (2006). Mathematical modeling of change of dynamic viscosity as a function of temperature and pressure of mineral oils for hydraulic systems. *Facta Universitatis. Series: Mechanical Engineering*.
18. Shamuratov, J.U. (2023). Physical quantity measured by a vibration viscometer. *Actual Problems of Modern Science, Education and Training*, 3.
19. Mills, K.C., Chapman, L.A., Fox, A.B., Sridhar, S. (2001). 'Round robin' project on the estimation of slag viscosities. *Scandinavian Journal of Metallurgy*, 30(6), 396–403.
20. Matyakubova, P., Ismatullaev, P., Shamuratov, J. (2023). Development of vibration viscometer for industrial purpose and experience of its practice. In: *Proc. IV Int. Scientific Conf. "Construction Mechanics, Hydraulics and Water Resources Engineering"*, Aug. 2023, Tashkent, Uzbekistan. *E3S Web of Conferences*, Vol. 365. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202336505012>
21. Coker, K. (2007). In: *Ludwig's Applied Process Design for Chemical and Petrochemical Plants*, Vol. 1 (4th ed.).
22. Micha, P. (2017). Temperature-viscosity models reassessed. *Critical Reviews in Food Science and Nutrition*, 15, 2663–2672.
23. Markova, L.V., Makarenko, V.M., Semenyuk, M.S., Zozulya, A.P. (2010). On-line monitoring of the viscosity of lubricating oils. *Journal of Friction and Wear*, 31, 433–442.

ФИЛИАЛ РОССИЙСКОГО
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОГО
УНИВЕРСИТЕТА НЕФТИ И ГАЗА
(СНИУ) ИМЕНИ И.М. ГУБКИНА

ИННОВАЦИИ В НЕФТЕГАЗОВОЙ ОТРАСЛИ

ТОМ 6, НОМЕР 2

INNOVATIONS IN THE OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY

VOLUME 6, ISSUE 2

Editorial staff of the journals of www.tadqiqot.uz
Tadqiqot LLC the city of Tashkent,
Amir Temur Street pr.1, House 2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Phone: (+998-94) 404-0000

Контакт редакций журналов. www.tadqiqot.uz
ООО Тадқиқот город Ташкент,
улица Амира Темура пр.1, дом-2.
Web: <http://www.tadqiqot.uz/>; Email: info@tadqiqot.uz
Тел: (+998-94) 404-0000